

Studies in the Cotarnine Series. Part VII. Action of Sulphuric Acid on Cotarnine: Formation of Methylene-bisphenol-betaine of 2-Methyl-6:7-dihydroxy-8-methoxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinolinium Hydroxide.

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The investigation of the reactivity of the *ana*-hydrogen atom in the narcotine bases has revealed a curious difference between narcotine and hydrocotarnine on the one hand and cotarnine on the other. The former react smoothly with aldehydes in the presence of sulphuric acid to give crystalline dimolecular compounds of the following type :

Cotarnine, however, behaves very differently and remains either unchanged or yields only small amounts of impure amorphous products. This was particularly noticeable in the case of the condensation with formaldehyde which led with hydrocotarnine to the formation of the theoretical quantity of methylene dihydrocotarnine in the course of twelve hours, whereas under identical conditions, no new product could be isolated with cotarnine. This departure from the normal course led to attempts to bring about the reaction by varying the conditions and eventually to a careful study of the action of sulphuric acid alone on cotarnine.

The action of sulphuric acid on the opium alkaloids has been studied by many investigators.*

By treatment with 82% sulphuric acid or 73% sulphuric acid at 80° Bandow (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1747) obtained from hydrocotarnine a new base which he named hydrodicotarnine and assigned to it the formula $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2$, the reaction was represented thus :—

* Arpe, *Annalen*, 1845, 58, 96; Laurent and Gerhardt, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1848, *iii*, 24, 112; Mathiessen and Wright, *Ann. Suppl.*, 1870, 7, 170; Armstrong, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1871, 25, 56; Fulton, *J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1928, 13, 750; Kitasato and Goto, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2696.

Freund and Daube (*Ber.*, 1912, **45**, 1183), who repeated this work, showed conclusively that the product isolated was identical with methylene dihydrocotarnine (I), a substance prepared subsequently in theoretical yield from the condensation of hydrocotarnine and formaldehyde under the influence of sulphuric acid. They explained the formation of this base by assuming that the first effect of sulphuric acid on hydrocotarnine in Bandow's experiment was to demethylenate the base, formaldehyde and a phenolic body (2-methyl-6:7-dihydroxy-8-methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroisoquinoline) being formed: The formaldehyde, split off in the reaction, then condensed with unchanged hydrocotarnine in the presence of sulphuric acid to form methylene dihydrocotarnine (I),

In the present investigation it is found that the reaction takes a different course when cotarnine is treated with sulphuric acid under conditions very similar to those of Bandow. After standing for three days at room temperature, the acid solution, which acquired a scarlet-red colour, threw down, on basification, a considerable amount of a beautiful orange-yellow substance, m. p. 302-304° (decomp.).

It is necessary to mention here that the duration of the experiment, the concentration of the acid employed and the quantity of the acid are important factors in getting the desired result.

The compound is a fairly strong base and dissolves readily in dilute mineral acids. The dihydrochloride and the dihydrobromide of the base have been obtained in a crystalline condition while with nitric acid it has been possible to prepare both the mono- and the dinitrate. As a phenolic base it dissolves in cold dilute caustic soda to a deep red solution from which it is reprecipitated on treatment with carbon dioxide, and with ferric chloride it gives a dark green colour. The phenolic character of the base is further demonstrated by the easy formation of a methyl ether insoluble in alkalis. Acetylation and

benzoylation, however, have not been successful only impure products being obtained. The completely demethylated base and its hydriodide have also been obtained by the action of hydriodic acid under pressure. The quaternary ammonium iodide of the base, which was formed very readily, could not be degraded by the usual Hofmann method, but regenerated the original phenolic base on treatment with caustic soda. This clearly indicates the presence in the molecule of a phenol-betaine ring which alone could account for the observed change. The significance of this reaction will be best understood from the following scheme :

Similarly, the methiodide of the methoxy compound reacted with alkali regenerating the free methoxy base.

The foregoing experimental facts together with Freund's interpretation of the action of sulphuric acid on hydrocotarnine (*loc. cit.*) have made it possible to arrive at an understanding of the mechanism of the formation of this base from cotarnine under the influence of sulphuric acid.

In acid medium cotarnine changes from the aldehydeimino form (II) to the ammonium form (III), the latter being gradually demethylated by sulphuric acid into an intermediate phenolic body (IV) and formaldehyde. The loss of sulphuric acid from (IV) results in the formation of a compound with a betaine ring (V). The reaction does not, however, end here, but the formaldehyde split off in the reaction subsequently condenses with (V) at the reactive 5-position and forms methylene-bis-phenol-betaine of 2-methyl-6:7-dihydroxy-8-methoxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinolinium hydroxide (VI).

The methylene dicotarnine structure (VI) for the new base has been based mainly on the ground that it forms definitely both a mono- and a dinitrate and that the molecular weight of its methyl ether corresponds to the dimolecular formula. The molecular weight of the phenolic base could not be determined satisfactorily on account of its sparing solubility in all ordinary solvents and in camphor. The phenolic base gives only a monomethiodide and a monoethiodide while the methylated base forms the normal dimethiodide. The difference which may be due to steric factors is difficult to explain. Freund and Reitz (*Ber*, 1909, 39, 2233) who made a similar observation with bishydrocotarnine expressed the view that the combination of the dimolecular base with only one molecule of methyl iodide should be attributed to steric hindrance. Another presumptive evidence in favour of the dimolecular formula of the new base is to be found in the sparing solubility of all of its salts with mineral acids. The salts of cotarnine and hydrocotarnine and their simple derivatives with mineral acids are all very soluble in water, while those of bishydrocotarnine, methylene dicotarnine, nitrobenzoyl and nitrobenzylidene cotarnine and all similar bases having a high molecular weight are, as a rule, found to be characterised by their sparing solubility.

Many attempts have been made to place the formula on unassailable ground by oxidising the base and obtaining a product of known structure, but without success.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methylene bis-phenol-betaine of 2-Methyl-6:7-dihydroxy-8-methoxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinolinium Hydroxide (VI, R=Me, R'=H) (compound A).

Cotarnine (5 g.) was dissolved in ice-cold 90 % sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) and the mixture left for 3 days at room temperature. The solution which acquired a deep scarlet colour was then poured into ice-water and basified with ammonia. The yellow crystalline precipitate, that gradually separated out, was filtered after 2 hours and dried on a plate. The crude product weighed 4.0 g., m. p. 302°-304°. It was crystallised from a large excess of boiling alcohol as glistening dark yellow needles, m.p. 308° (decomp.), yield 3 g. [Found (in a sample dried in vacuum over quicklime for 24 hours): C, 62.13; H, 6.25; N, 6.71; OMe, 13.45; H₂O (on heating over P₂O₅ at 110°/5 mm.), 3.40. C₂₃H₂₆O₆N₂. H₂O requires C, 62.16; H, 6.30; N, 6.31; OMe, 13.96; H₂O 4.05 per cent].

It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, chloroform and acetone, insoluble in benzene and ether and readily soluble in hot aniline.

The *Dihydrochloride* was prepared by adding a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid to a suspension of the base in absolute alcohol. The clear solution which resulted very quickly deposited light yellow needles, m.p. 200° (decomp.). [Found (in air-dried substance): Cl, 13.20. C₂₃H₂₆O₆N₂, 2HCl requires Cl, 14.22 per cent].

The *Dihydrobromide* was prepared in the same manner. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 212° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 26.71. C₂₃H₂₆O₆N₂, 2HBr requires Br, 27.20 per cent).

The *Mononitrate*.—The base (0.5 g.) was dissolved in N-HNO₃ (1 c.c.). The clear solution on standing deposited light yellow needles. It was recrystallised from hot water as colourless fibrous needles, m.p. 222°. (Found: N, 8.49. C₂₃H₂₇O₉N₃ requires N, 8.58 per cent).

The *Dinitrate* was prepared by treating the base (0.5 g.) with NHNO₃ (2 c.c.). The clear solution on standing deposited light yellow needles. This was very soluble in water but could be recrystallised from absolute alcohol as needles, m. p. 93°. (Found: N, 9.90. C₂₃H₂₈O₁₂N₄ requires N, 10.14 per cent).

The *Platinichloride* came down in orange-red plates on adding chloroplatinic acid to a solution of the base in concentrated hydrochloric acid, m. p. 198° (decomp.). [Found: H₂O (at 110°-120°), 2.09. C₂₃H₂₆O₆N₂, 2HCl, PtCl₄, H₂O requires H₂O, 2.09 per cent.]. The

anhydrous salt was analysed for platinum. [Found Pt, 23.01. $C_{23}H_{26}O_6N_2$, 2HCl, $PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 23.23 per cent].

The *Dipicrate* was prepared by adding excess of saturated aqueous picric acid solution to a solution of the base in very dilute hydrochloric acid. It separated from alcohol as stout, straw-yellow prisms, m. p. 230° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.92. $C_{36}H_{32}O_{20}N_8$ requires N, 12.66 per cent).

The *Monomethiodide* was prepared by heating the components in a pressure bottle at 100° for 2 hours and recrystallising the dark yellow product from hot water. It formed straw-yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 220° (decomp.). [Found: C, 49.23; H, 5.38; N, 5.02; H_2O (at 110°/5mm over P_2O_5), 3.42. $C_{24}H_{29}O_6N_2I$, H_2O requires C, 49.14; H, 5.29; N, 4.77; H_2O , 3.05 per cent].

Action of Caustic Soda on the Monomethiodide.—The monomethiodide (1 g.) was dissolved in 2*N*-caustic soda (20 c.c.) and the solution heated on the steam-bath for half an hour. The solution was then cooled in ice and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and ammonia was added till the solution was faintly alkaline. On standing yellow crystals separated out. These were filtered and recrystallised from alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 308°, not depressed by admixture with (VI, R'=H, R=Me). The hydrochloride, the picrate and the methoxy derivative of this product were identical with the hydrochloride, the picrate and the methoxy derivative of the parent base. The yield of the regenerated base was 0.6 g.

The *Monoethiodide* was prepared in the same manner. It crystallised from hot water in rectangular plates, m. p. 222°. The substance was dried at 110°/5 mm. for analysis. (Found: I, 21.44. $C_{25}H_{31}O_6N_2I$ requires I, 21.82 per cent).

Demethylation with HI. Formation of Methylene-bis-phenol-betaine of 2-methyl-6:7:8-trihydroxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinolinium Hydroxide (VI, R'=H, R=H).

The base (1 g.) and freshly distilled hydriodic acid (5 c. c.) were heated together in a sealed tube at 130°-140° for 5 hours. The excess of hydriodic acid was distilled off and the dark periodide was left in contact with sulphurous acid for 2 hours. The hydroiodide gradually separated out in light yellow needles. Recrystallisation from hot water gave bright yellow needles, m. p. 220° (decomp.). The free base was obtained by decomposing the salt with ammonia and crystallising the yellow precipitate from a large excess of boiling alcohol as dark yellow needles. m. p. 275° (decomp.). [Found (air-dried sample): I, 39.61. $C_{21}H_{22}O_6N_2$, 2HI requires I, 38.83 per cent].

The *Dinitrate* was obtained as a crystalline precipitate by rubbing the base with a few drops of dilute nitric acid. It was recrystallised from hot water as colourless fibrous needles, m. p. 195° (decomp.).

Methylation with Dimethylsulphate. Formation of Methylenebisphenol-betaine of 2-Methyl-6:8-dimethoxy-7-hydroxy-3:4-dihydro isoquinolinium Hydroxide (VI, $R' = Me$ $R = Me$) (Compound B).

The base, m.p. 308° , (2 g.) was dissolved in 2 *N*-caustic soda (10 c.c.), dimethyl sulphate (2 c.c.) was added and the mixture vigorously shaken. The methoxy compound separated out quickly as a light yellow crystalline precipitate, which was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from hot water as long yellow needles, m.p. 268° (decomp.), yield 1.6 g. [Found: C, 66.06; H, 7.04; N, 5.88; OMe, 26.7; M.W. (Rast method), 418.4. $C_{25}H_{30}O_6N_2$ requires C, 66.08; H, 6.60; N, 6.16; OMe, 27.31 per cent. M.W., 454.0].

The identical compound was obtained when a mixture of the base (1 g.) dissolved in dilute caustic soda (4 c.c.) and excess of methyl iodide was heated in a pressure bottle at 100° for 1 hour. On cooling yellow crystals separated out. These were filtered and recrystallised from hot water as yellow needles melting at 268° (mixed m.p.).

The mother liquor from the above on acidification threw down a yellow precipitate of the methiodide which crystallised from hot water in yellow needles, melting at 180° (mixed m.p.) (*vide infra*).

The *Dihydrochloride* was prepared by treating a suspension of the above base in water with dilute hydrochloric acid. The hydrochloride crystallised from hot water in clusters of needles, m.p. 191° (decomp.). [Found (in a sample dried at $110-20^{\circ}$): Cl, 12.72. $C_{25}H_{30}O_6N_2$, 2HCl requires Cl, 13.47 per cent].

The *Dinitrate*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from hot water in fibrous needles, m.p. 235° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.49. $C_{25}H_{30}O_6N_2$, 2HNO₃ requires N, 9.65 per cent).

The *Platinichloride* came down as orange-red plates, m.p. 248° (decomp.). The *picrate*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from alcohol in yellow prisms, m.p. 114° .

The *Dimethiodide* crystallised from hot water in long yellow plates, m.p. 180° (decomp.). (Found: I, 33.96. $C_{27}H_{36}O_6N_2I_2$ requires I, 34.42 per cent).

Action of Caustic Soda on the Methiodide.—The methiodide (1 g.) was dissolved in warm 2*N*-caustic soda (4 c.c.) and the solution heated to 60° on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The clear solution, on standing

deposited yellow needles. These were collected and recrystallised from hot water as bright yellow needles, m.p. 268°, not depressed by admixture with (VI, R'=Me, R=Me).

Action of Nascent Hydrogen on the Methiodide of Compound B. Formation of Methylene-bis-2-methyl-6:7:8-trimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-isoquinoline.

The methiodide of the base B (0.5 g.) was treated with 4*N*-H₂SO₄ (10 c.c.) and zinc dust (1 g.), and the mixture was heated on the water-bath. The solution which was at first yellow gradually became colourless in about 10 minutes and after heating for another 30 minutes, the solution was filtered from the excess of zinc, cooled strong ammonia added and the liquid extracted thrice with ether. The ether solution dried over anhydrous K₂CO₃ and the ether distilled off. The crystalline residue was recrystallised from alcohol as colourless prisms, m.p. 201°. (Found: C, 66.95; H, 7.51. C₂₇H₃₈O₆N₂ requires C, 66.67; H, 7.81 per cent).

SUMMARY.

Cotarnine, in the presence of 90% sulphuric acid, undergoes a deep-seated change. The acid is supposed first to demethylenate the base, formaldehyde and a phenolic body (2-methyl-6:7-dihydroxy-8-methoxy-3:4-dihydro-isoquinolinium sulphate) being formed. The latter loses sulphuric acid and a phenolic compound with a betaine ring (phenol-betaine of 2-methyl-6:7-dihydroxy-8-methoxy-3:4-dihydro-isoquinolinium hydroxide) is formed. The formaldehyde, split off in the reaction, then condenses with the 'phenol-betaine compound' at the reactive *ana*-(5-) position, forming methylene-bis-phenol-betaine of 2-methyl-6:7-dihydroxy-8-methoxy-3:4-dihydro-isoquinolinium hydroxide.

The analyses of the new base, its methyl ether, their salts and their methiodides have been found to be in complete harmony with the above constitution for the base.

Fig. 1

Methylene-bis-phenol-betaine of 2-methyl-6:7-dihydroxy-8-methoxy-1:4-dihydroisoquinolinium hydroxide (Compound A).

Fig 2

Mononitrate of Comp. A

Fig. 3

Platinichloride of Comp. A.

Fig. 4

Monomethide of Comp. A

Fig. 5

Methylene-bis-phenol-betaine of 2-methyl-6 : 8-dimethoxy-7 hydroxy-3 : 4-dihydroisoquinolinium hydroxide (Compound B).

Fig. 6

Dihydrochloride of Comp. B.

Fig. 8

Platinichloride of Compound B.

Fig. 7

Dinitrate of Compound B.

Fig. 9

Dimethide of Compound B.

